

Research

Evaluation of Commercial Motorcycle Operators' Awareness and Impact of National Road Traffic Regulations in Ogbomosho Metropolis, Oyo State

Abigail Bako^{1*}

¹Msc. Research and Public Policy, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ibadan.

Abstract: The primary objective of this study is to examine the factors that are responsible for the low awareness and impact of traffic regulations. A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods was employed, utilizing the statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS), and 400 commercial motorcycle riders were sampled to respond to an assessed research questionnaire in Ogbomosho metropolis, Oyo State. The factors responsible for awareness and impact were used to evaluate the operations of commercial riders, and the findings of the study revealed a significant level of low awareness of traffic signs and symbols and a mixed low impact of traffic regulations. These factors have a great impact on reducing road crash injuries and smooth operations in Ogbomosho, thereby informing policymakers and stakeholders on policies involving educational programs and safety campaigns. Important improvements in compliance with road traffic regulations and addressing challenges faced by commercial riders.

Keywords: Awareness, Impact, Commercial Motorcycle Riders, Ogbomosho

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 10 September, 2023; **Published:** 6 October, 2023

How to cite this article: Abigail Bako (2023). Evaluation of Commercial Motorcycle Operators' Awareness and Impact of National Road Traffic Regulations in Ogbomosho Metropolis, Oyo State. *North American Academic Research*, 6(8), 1-17. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8411622>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2023 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Motorcycle safety is a significant problem in Africa. (AFDB, July 2022) [1]. On average, 22.5% of road traffic deaths in 2016 involved riders or passengers on motorcycles, according to the data published by the World Health Organization (WHO 2018) [2]. It is important to note. 30% of all road crash deaths involve motorcycles, and the numbers are rising (WHO, 2022) [3].

The demography of Nigeria is so wide that, in terms of transportation, the vehicles are not sufficient to cover this large mass. Therefore, motorcycles constitute one of the most accessible and cheap means of transportation and the most usual form of informal transport. According to the revised highway code of the Federal Road Safety Commission of Nigeria [4], the chances are 8:10 that it would result in death or very serious injury. This means commercial

motorcycle riders pay no or little attention to road safety regulations, leading to road traffic accidents that involve other road users.

The many challenges faced by commercial motorcycle riders seem to be high, especially from non-adherence to road traffic regulation, traffic safety rules, and attitudinal problems from the intake of substances, especially alcohol, by motorcycle riders. The study is designed to address the gap that would justifiably minimize motorcycle accidents, thereby increasing the effectiveness of national road traffic regulations. The aim is to examine the factors that are responsible for low awareness and effectiveness of traffic regulations and to assess the extent to which they have knowledge of the traffic symbols.

National Road Traffic Regulations

The regulations are established by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC), which is the primary agency responsible for road safety in Nigeria. The FRSC, in collaboration with other relevant government agencies, formulates and enforces the national road traffic regulations [4].

Some of the key areas covered by the National Road Traffic Regulations include:

Licensing and Registration: The regulations stipulate the requirements for obtaining a driver's license and the registration of vehicles. They specify the procedures, qualifications, and conditions for obtaining and renewing licenses, as well as the registration process for vehicles.

Traffic Control and Signs: The regulations provide guidelines for traffic control, including the use of traffic signs, signals, and road markings. They define the meanings of different road signs and signals, as well as the procedures to be followed at intersections, roundabouts, and other traffic control points.

Speed Limits: The regulations establish speed limits for different types of roads, such as highways, urban areas, and residential zones. They outline the maximum speed limits that road users should adhere to in order to ensure safety and prevent accidents.

Vehicle Maintenance and Safety: The regulations set standards for vehicle maintenance and safety. They specify the requirements for vehicle inspections, roadworthiness, and the use of safety devices such as seat belts, headlights, and brake lights.

Prohibited Acts: The regulations outline acts that are considered illegal and prohibited on the roads. These may include driving under the influence of alcohol or drugs, using mobile phones while driving, overloading vehicles, and reckless driving.

Enforcement and Penalties: The regulations provide for enforcement mechanisms and penalties for violations. They empower law enforcement agencies to apprehend offenders and impose fines, penalties, or other sanctions as prescribed by the law.

The theoretical framework for the study on the awareness and effectiveness of national road traffic regulation on commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso Metropolis, Oyo State, is based on the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). Developed by Albert Bandura, SCT emphasizes the reciprocal interaction between an individual's cognitive processes, behavior, and the social environment.

Methodology

The targeted respondents are the commercial motorcycle riders belonging to motorcycle riders' union, operating on the major highway and road paths. The total number of four hundred commercial motorcycle riders working in Ogbomoso, Oyo State were sampled for the study. They were presented in descriptive form using the distribution pattern and summary; frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations and Chi Squares analyses for qualitative variables. The analysis of variance, correlation and regression analyses will be employed where necessary.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Socio-demographic data of the commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso

Age	Frequency (Valid %)
15-20 years	9(3.1)
21-30 years	94 (31.9)
31-40 years	133 (45.1)
41-50 years	54 (18.3)
51-60 years	5 (1.7)
Educational Levels	
No Formal Education	45 (15.2)
Primary School	90 (30.4)
SSCE	152 (51.4)
NCE	7 (2.4)
OND/HND	2 (0.7)
Marital Status	
Single	62 (20.9)
Married	231 (77.8)
Divorced	3 (1)
Separated	1 (0.3)
Riding as a part-time work	
Yes	129 (43.6)
No	167 (56.2)
Union Membership	
No Union	167 (56.04)
ACOMORAN	36 (12.08)
ANACOWA	17 (5.7)
Muslim Riders	3 (1.01)
NURTW	34 (11.41)
Park Management System	13 (4.36)

RTEAN	24 (8.05)
TRAMAO	4 (1.34)

The findings indicate that many commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso Metropolis fall within the age range of 31–40 years (133 respondents, 36.1%). This group represents the major working force in the area. This is similar to the works of Ebeigbe and Obahiagbon (2012), Mitka (2010), and Sunday (2010) [5] [6] [7]. The study reveals that a significant proportion of commercial motorcycle riders have limited education, as previously reported by Adesola et al. (2022) and Achigbu and Ezepeue (2014) [8] [9]. The highest number of respondents, 152 (51.4%), held a senior secondary school certificate, while 90 (30.4%) had only attended primary school. Furthermore, 45 (15.2%) respondents had no formal education, and a small percentage, 7 (2.4%), were NCE holders. This suggests that a majority of the riders have a lower level of formal education, which may impact their understanding of road signs and regulations. This agrees with Prajapati and Nagar (2022) [10].

The results show that married individuals make up the majority of commercial motorcycle riders, accounting for 231 (77.8%) of the respondents. Meanwhile, 62 (20.9%) riders were single, 3 (1%) were divorced, and 1 (0.3%) were separated. The high percentage of married riders implies a need for increased responsibility and caution while riding. This agrees with Lim et al. (2022) and Yang et al. (2022) [11] [12].

The study reveals that a larger proportion of commercial motorcycle riders work on a full-time basis, with 167 (56.2%) respondents being full-time riders. On the other hand, 129 (43.6%) respondents engage in riding as a part-time occupation. This finding suggests that there is a significant level of unemployment in society, leading individuals to rely on motorcycle riding as a means of livelihood. This agrees with Barone and Lo Iacono (2014) [13].

The results indicates that a majority of the commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso Metropolis are not union members, accounting for 167 (56.04%) of the sampled population. Among those who are union members, the largest representation is from ACOMORAN with 36 (12.08%) respondents, followed by NURTW with 34 (11.41%) respondents, RTEAN with 24 (8.05%) respondents, ANACOWA with 17 (5.7%) respondents, and Park Management System with 13 (4.36%) respondents. These figures reflect the varying union affiliations among commercial motorcycle riders in the area. Mitka (2010) and Sunday (2010) [6] [7]. This similar to the works of Ebeigbe and Obahiagbon [5].

Table 2: Awareness of Road Traffic Regulation on Motorcycle

	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	
	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)	Means
There is speed limit for the movement of commercial motorcycle riders within Ogbomoso metropolis.	89 (30)	57 (19.2)	151 (50.8)	2.2088
I know is a must to register my motorcycle with the road safety authority	73 (24.6)	28 (9.4)	196 (66)	2.4141
I know that training of commercial motorcycle riding is very important	83 (27.9)	19(6.4)	195(65.7)	2.3771

I ensure to obtain necessary licenses from relevant authorities for smooth operation	70 (23.6)	27 (9.1)	200(67.7)	2.4377
I always check and replace engine oil as at when due.	17 (5.7)	22 (7.4)	258 (86.9)	2.8114
I understand the necessity to replacing the brake/clutch/Chain/Tyres/Throttle only when they are worn-out	20 (6.7)	9 (3)	268 (90.2)	2.835
I understand the necessity to replacing brake/clutch/Chain/Tyres/Throttle at regular interval	19 (6.4)	20 (6.7)	258 (86.9)	2.8047
I know the need to ensure the mirror/ horn/ lights/ indicators are in good working condition	25 (8.4)	18 (6.1)	254 (85.5)	2.771
I always ensure to replace mirror/ horn/ lights/ indicators when damage/ spoilt.	31 (10.4)	15 (5.1)	251 (84.5)	2.7407
I am always careful to replace damaged parts with second-handed spare parts.	33 (11.1)	34 (11.4)	230 (77.4)	2.8013
I am always careful to replace damaged parts with new spare parts when needed.	34 (11.4)	8 (2.7)	255 (85.9)	2.7441
I am aware of the use of helmet	19 (6.4)	24 (8.1)	253 (85.5)	2.7905
I know the use of headphones is prohibited	55 (18.5)	15 (5.1)	227 (76.4)	2.7172
I am aware of the importance of mirror usage during operation	20 (6.7)	17 (5.7)	260 (87.5)	2.8081
I always ensure my mirror is well positioned during operation	24 (8.1)	17 (5.7)	256 (86.2)	2.7811
I always carry one passenger per ride	34 (11.4)	11 (3.7)	252 (84.8)	2.734
If necessary, sometimes I carry more than one passenger while working	30 (10.1)	18 (6.1)	249 (83.8)	2.7374
I am to keeping to the right side of the road and check the traf-fics while overtaking	18 (6.1)	19 (6.4)	260 (87.5)	2.8148
I do have the understanding of the other road users such as pedestrians, motorist and accord them needed respect etc.	29 (9.8)	26 (8.8)	242 (81.5)	2.7172
I always maintain gap with other road users during operation	23 (7.7)	12 (4)	261 (88.2)	2.8041

I think it's necessary for me and passengers to sit properly while riding	24 (8.1)	18 (6.1)	255 (85.9)	2.7778
I always ensure to avoid blind areas while riding	36 (12.1)	12 (4)	249 (83.8)	2.7172
I am aware of the presence of traffic signs/ symbols along the road during operation	67 (22.6)	23 (7.7)	207 (69.7)	2.4714

The results obtained highlights the perceptions and attitudes of commercial motorcycle riders regarding various aspects of road traffic regulations. The findings indicate that 151 (50.8%) respondents agreed that there is a speed limit for motorcycle riders, while 89 (30%) disagreed. This suggests a mixed understanding of the speed limits among the respondents (Lemonakis et al., 2021) [12]. According to the results, 196 (66%) respondents affirmed the importance of motorcycle registration by mandatory authorities, while 73 (24.6%) respondents disagreed. This suggests a majority recognition of the necessity of motorcycle registration (Ngoan, 2021) [15].

The findings reveal that 196 (65.7%) respondents recognized the importance of training for commercial motorcycle riders, while 83 (27.9%) respondents disagreed. This indicates a significant proportion of respondents acknowledging the value of training (Singh, 2020) [16]

The results shows that 200 (67.7%) respondents emphasized the need for a license for commercial motorcycle riders issued by the authority, while 70 (23.6%) respondents objected to this requirement. This suggests a general understanding of the importance of having a valid license (Almutairi et al., 2023) [17]. The results indicates that a high percentage of respondents prioritize maintenance practices such as checking and replacing engine oil when due (258 respondents, 86.9%), replacing brake/clutch/tyre (268 respondents, 90.2%), and ensuring the mirror is in working condition (254 respondents, 85.5%). This indicates a positive attitude towards maintaining their motorcycles in good condition (Koyama et al., 2022) [18].

According to the findings, 253 (85.5%) respondents agreed to the use of helmets, while 19 (6.4%) respondents disagreed. This suggests a general awareness of the importance of helmet usage among the majority of respondents (Kumphong, 2018) [19]. Overall, the results provide insights into the perceptions and awareness of commercial motorcycle riders regarding road traffic regulations. It indicates both areas of agreement and areas where further education and awareness may be needed to enhance compliance and safety among motorcycle riders (Yellappan et al., 2019) [20].

The results obtained sheds light on the knowledge and compliance of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis regarding various traffic regulations. The findings indicate that 200 (67.35%) respondents affirm compliance with using a helmet, while 97 (32.7%) respondents never use a helmet. This suggests that a significant proportion of respondents are compliant with helmet usage (Kumphong, 2018; Burtscher et al., 2013) [19] [21]. According to the results, 209 (70.4%) respondents affirm their understanding of the merits of helmets in preventing dangerous crash injuries, while 88 (9.6%) respondents do not comply with the importance of helmets. This highlights the majority of respondents' knowledge of the benefits of wearing a helmet (Abid et al., 2022) [22].

The results reveal that 189 (63.9%) respondents have never been fined for using headphones while operating their motorcycles, while 108 (36.4%) respondents have received fines. This suggests that a significant number of respondents are not compliant with regulations prohibiting the use of headphones (Pandey et al., 2015) [23].

The results indicate that 285 (96%) respondents always use mirrors during their motorcycle operations, while 12 (4%) respondents never use mirrors. This shows a high level of compliance with mirror usage among the majority of respondents. According to the results, 259 (87.2%) respondents affirm their compliance with obeying traffic controllers

during their operations, while 38 (12.8%) respondents do not comply. This suggests a significant level of adherence to traffic controllers' instructions (Kyriakidis et al., 2015) [24]. The results reveals that 181 (60.9%) respondents have experienced mishaps after purchasing new parts for their motorcycles, while 116 (39.1%) respondents have not. This indicates that a considerable number of respondents have encountered issues after replacing parts (Singh, 2020) [16]. The results indicate that 292 (98.3%) respondents affirm their stability during motorcycle operations, while 5 (1.7%) respondents do not feel stable. This suggests a high level of confidence and stability among the majority of respondents (Souchele corvec, 2021) [25]. According to the results, 277 (93.3%) respondents believe that intoxication is linked to unnecessary accidents, while 20 (6.7%) respondents do not consider it a cause. This highlights the understanding of the majority of respondents regarding the connection between intoxication and accidents (Karlberg et al., 1998) [26]. The results reveal that 163 (54.9%) respondents affirm their avoidance of riding when fatigued, while 134 (45.1%) respondents do not consider it a problem. This indicates that a significant number of respondents prioritize avoiding riding when fatigued (Rashad et al., 2018) [27]. The results show that respondents have varying perceptions of their speed limits, with 106 (35.7%) respondents considering 70 km/h as their speed limit, 89 (30%) respondents considering 90 km/h, 67 (22.6%) respondents considering 50 km/h, and 35 (11.8%) respondents considering 35 km/h. This suggests a range of understandings and compliance levels regarding speed limits ((Jongen et al., 2011) [28]. Overall, the results provide insights into the knowledge and compliance of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis with various traffic regulations. It highlights areas of compliance as well as areas where further education and awareness may be needed to improve adherence to road safety measures (Mumuni et al., 2023; Hagan et al., 2021; Ogunkeyede and Osungbade, 2019) [29] [30] [31].

Table 3: Effectiveness of Road Traffic Regulations on Commercial Motorcycle Riders in Ogbomoso

Effectiveness of keeping to Traffic regulations	No	Yes	Mean
	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)	
1. Do you comply to the use of helmet?	97 (32.7)	200(67.3)	0.673
2. Has helmet been of any advantage to you during operation?	88 (9.6)	209(70.4)	0.704
3. Have you been fine for the use of head-phone while on operation?	189(63.9)	108(36.4)	0.37
4. Do you use the mirror during operation?	12(4)	285(96)	0.973
5. Do you obey the traffic controller during operation?	38 (12.8)	259(87.2)	0.872
6. After purchase of parts, have you experience any mishap?	116 (39.1)	181(60.9)	0.609
7. Are you mentally stable while on operation?	5(1.7)	292(98.3)	0.983
8. I avoid riding anytime I am intoxicated.	20 (6.7)	277(93.3)	0.933

9. Do you link most unnecessary accidents to intoxication?	134 (45.1)	163(54.9)	0.549	
10. I avoid riding anytime I am fatigued.	24 (8.1)	273(91.9)	0.919	
11. Do you link most unnecessary accidents to fatigue?	130 (43.8)	167(56.2)	0.562	
	30km/h	50km/h	70km/h	90km/h or more
	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)	Freq. (%)
Speed limit for normal operation?	35(11.8)	67(22.6)	106(35.7)	89 (30)

The results obtained offers insights into the effectiveness of existing policies and the compliance of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis with these laws. The findings indicate that 293 (98.3%) respondents are complained with using headlights and pointers during their operations, while 4 (1.3%) respondents are ineffective in their use. This suggests a high level of compliance with this particular regulation (Elevelt et al., 2021) [32].

According to the results, 240 (81.1%) respondents are compliant with traffic control during their operations, while 19 (6.4%) respondents are non-compliant. This indicates a substantial level of compliance with traffic control measures among the majority of respondents (Sroka, 2022) [33].

The results reveal that 200 (67.6%) respondents affirm compliance with attending training school, while 59 (19.9%) respondents oppose the perceived ineffectiveness of the training provided by relevant authorities. This suggests a reasonable level of compliance with training requirements.

On compliance with path roads, the results show that 291 (73.7%) respondents are compliant with using roads that are not constructed for commercial motorcycle riders, while 31 (10.4%) respondents are non-compliant. This indicates a significant proportion of respondents adhere to the designated paths. According to the data, 257 (86.5%) respondents are compliant with safe riding practices, while 15 (5.1%) respondents are non-compliant, particularly regarding bad road conditions. This highlights a considerable level of compliance with safe riding habits (Rashad et al., 2018; Midgley, 2014) [27] [34]. The results indicate that 208 (86.5%) respondents are compliant with renewing their paper fees, while 39 (13.1%) respondents are non-compliant. This suggests a majority of respondents adhere to the requirement of renewing their documentation.

The findings reveal that 232 (78.1%) respondents are compliant with paying union dues, while 18 (6.1%) respondents are non-compliant. This indicates a significant level of compliance with union fee payments. According to the data, 255 (85.9%) respondents are compliant with the extortion demands of officers, while 20 (6.7%) respondents do not comply with police/authority extortion on the road. This suggests that a significant number of respondents experience and comply with extortion demands (Adisa et al., 2018) [35].

On impact of high motorcycle costs, the results show that 246 (82.8%) respondents acknowledge that the high cost of motorcycles affects their investment decisions, while 14 (4.7%) respondents are non-compliant and prefer to purchase second-hand motorcycles. This highlights the perception of cost as a factor influencing compliance. Overall, the data provides insights into the compliance levels of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis with various policies and regulations. While the majority of respondents demonstrate compliance in several areas, there are instances of non-compliance and perceived ineffectiveness. These findings can be used to assess the effectiveness of existing policies and identify areas where further enforcement or awareness measures may be needed to improve compliance.

Table 4: Accidents Flashpoints

	Positive Responses	Re-Percent	F. Exp	F. Obs- F.Exp	(F.Obs- F.Exp)^2	((F. Obs- F.Exp)^2)/F.Exp
Isale Ora	109	10.200	4.762	5.438	29.572	6.210
UnderG	74	6.900	4.762	2.138	4.571	0.960
Molete	15	1.400	4.762	-3.362	11.302	2.374
Ojagbo	79	7.400	4.762	2.638	6.959	1.462
Sabo	88	8.300	4.762	3.538	12.518	2.629
Aroje	13	1.200	4.762	-3.562	12.687	2.664
Ile Ewe	40	3.800	4.762	-0.962	0.925	0.194
Agboowo/Owode	89	8.400	4.762	3.638	13.235	2.780
Oke Aanu	37	3.500	4.762	-1.262	1.592	0.334
Araada/Oragada	62	5.800	4.762	1.038	1.077	0.226
Takie	153	14.400	4.762	9.638	92.892	19.508
Stadium	14	1.300	4.762	-3.462	11.984	2.517
High School	45	4.200	4.762	-0.562	0.315	0.066
Caretaker	46	4.300	4.762	-0.462	0.213	0.045
Federal	34	3.200	4.762	-1.562	2.439	0.512
Kere	6	0.600	4.762	-4.162	17.321	3.638
Ahoyaya	20	1.900	4.762	-2.862	8.190	1.720
IdiOro	12	1.100	4.762	-3.662	13.409	2.816
Adenike	11	1.000	4.762	-3.762	14.151	2.972
Orita Naira	48	4.500	4.762	-0.262	0.068	0.014
General	70	6.600	4.762	1.838	3.378	0.710
Total	1065	100.00%				54.350

The obtained results highlight the distribution of commercial motorcycle accidents in different areas of Ogbomoso metropolis. These statistics shed light on the areas where commercial motorcycle accidents are more prevalent. It is important to consider the factors that might contribute to these higher accident rates in specific areas. Factors such as traffic

congestion, road conditions, intersection design, presence of pedestrian activity, and adherence to traffic rules can influence accident occurrence. To provide a more comprehensive analysis, it is recommended to refer to local traffic accident reports or studies specific to Ogbomosho metropolis. These sources would provide more detailed insights into the causes and circumstances surrounding the accidents in each area. Understanding the specific areas with higher accident rates can assist local authorities and transportation planners in implementing targeted interventions and safety measures to mitigate accidents and enhance road safety in those locations. By focusing on these areas, efforts can be directed towards improving infrastructure, traffic management, and public awareness campaigns.

Table 5: Awareness of Road Traffic Signs/Symbols by Commercial Motorcycle Rider

	N	Percent	F.Exp	F. Obs- F.Exp	(F.Obs- F.Exp)^2	((F.Obs- F.Exp)^2)/F.Exp
Speed limit	20	1.437	6.25	-4.813	23.167	3.707
Bend Right/Left	81	5.819	6.25	-0.431	0.186	0.0297
No Right Turn	149	10.704	6.25	4.454	19.838	3.174
Carriageway	69	4.957	6.25	-1.293	1.672	0.268
Narrow						
T-Junction	184	13.218	6.25	6.968	48.559	7.769
No Stopping	83	5.963	6.25	-0.287	0.083	0.013
Speed limit	90	6.466	6.25	0.216	0.046	0.007
Maximum						
No U turn	156	11.207	6.25	4.957	24.571	3.931
Roundabout	133	9.555	6.25	3.305	10.920	1.747
U Turn	181	13.003	6.25	6.753	45.601	7.296
Hospital	42	3.017	6.25	-3.233	10.451	1.672
Direction Sig-	90	6.466	6.25	0.216	0.046	0.007
nals						
Centre and lane	30	2.155	6.25	-4.095	16.768	2.683
lines						
Edge and dou-	20	1.437	6.25	-4.813	23.167	3.707
ble lines						
Zebra Markings	21	1.509	6.25	-4.741	22.481	3.597

Straight and Bi-directional Arrows	43	3.089	6.25	-3.161	9.991	1.599
	1392	100.00%				41.208

The results obtained present the percentage of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis who are able to identify various traffic signs and symbols. These percentages represent the proportion of commercial motorcycle riders who can correctly identify each specific traffic sign or symbol. It indicates the level of awareness and knowledge among the riders regarding these regulatory signs. The ability of commercial motorcycle riders to recognize and understand traffic signs and symbols is crucial for their safety and the safety of other road users. Traffic signs provide important information about road conditions, rules, and potential hazards, allowing riders to make informed decisions while on the road. However, it is important to note that the percentages provided do not reflect a comprehensive understanding of all traffic signs and symbols by commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomoso metropolis. To gain a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of their knowledge, a broader survey or assessment that covers a wider range of traffic signs and symbols would be necessary. Additionally, it would be beneficial to provide training and educational programs to enhance the knowledge and awareness of commercial motorcycle riders regarding traffic signs and symbols. These initiatives can contribute to improving road safety and reducing the risk of accidents.

Correlation Table 6: Correlation Coefficient of Awareness Factor and Effectiveness of Traffic Regulations on Commercial Motorcycle Riders in Ogbomoso Metropolis.

	Awareness about Motorcycle Registration, Licensing and Traffic Signs	Awareness about Speed limit	Awareness about prohibition of Phone Accessories	Awareness to the use of Second-hand spare parts	Awareness about Safety Guide-lines	Traffic measures, Road factors and Parts maintenance
1. Awareness to proper maintenance cultures	0.368**	0.181**	0.275**	0.495**	-0.105	0.321**
2. Awareness of motorcycle		-0.012	0.567**	0.338**	0.324**	0.337**

registration, li-						
censing and traf-						
fic signs						
3. Awareness of			-0.082	0.1	0.104	-0.019
speed limit						
4. Awareness on				0.164**	0.113	0.157**
prohibition of						
Phone accesso-						
ries						
5. Awareness on					0.04	0.257**
the use of sec-						
ond-handed						
spare parts						
6. Compliance to	-0.105	0.324**	0.113	0.04	0.365	0.365**
the use of safety						
guides						

P < 0.05 – Significant

P < 0.01- Highly Significant

Awareness on Commercial Motorcycle maintenance culture is highly significant and positively related with the awareness to regulation on their motorcycle with the authorities to obtain relevant licenses and obeying traffic sign/symbols (0.368**), Awareness of Prohibition headphones accessories (0.275**), awareness on the use of second-hand spare parts (0.495) and the effectiveness of the traffic officers, road factors and part maintenance. Awareness on motorcycle registration, licensing and traffic signs is significantly related with prohibition of headphones and phones that is the Commercial riders are lecture on the danger while riding (0.567**), also related to the use of second-hand parts (0.338**), awareness of safety guidelines (0.324**) and significantly related with effectiveness of road factors and parts maintenance (0.337**).

Awareness on the speed limits amongst commercial riders is highly significant and positively related to compliance with the use of safety guidelines (0.324**). Compliance with the use of safety guidelines is positively related to traffic road and parts maintenance (0.365**)

Awareness on the use of second-hand parts to compliance of traffic road and part maintenance is highly significant and positively related for a better working condition while on operation (0.257**). Awareness on the prohibition of headphones and phones is highly significant and positively related to compliance with the road traffic and part maintenance (0.157**).

Table 7: The Regression Model for the Possibility of Commercial Motorcycle Accidents Rate in Ogbomoso Metropolis

$$P(\text{Accidents}) = 0.019 + 0.1(P(\text{Factors})) + 0.098(P(\text{Traffic Symbols})) + 0.02(\text{AggEffectiveness2}) - 0.007(\text{AggEffectiveness1}) + \epsilon$$

P(Accidents)	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Constant	0.019	0.038		0.486	0.620	-0.057	0.095
P(Factors)	0.100	0.025	0.24	3.932	0.000	0.05	0.149
P(Traffic Symbols)	0.098	0.031	0.195	3.154	0.002	0.037	0.159
AggEffectiveness2	0.020	0.01	0.121	2.082	0.038	0.001	0.039
AggEffectiveness1	-0.007	0.024	-0.018	-0.298	0.766	-0.054	0.04

As shown by the model in the table 12, for every 1 unit change in the probability of motorcycle accidents happening, factors attributed to accidents account for 0.1, traffic symbols account for 0.098, why the road factor/ part maintenance account for 0.02 with all of them having significant effect.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings uncover a number of riders began riding motorcycles at an underage, and the majority of them did not undergo formal training before engaging in commercial riding. The study reveals that awareness of road traffic regulations showed a mixed knowledge among respondents, while the effectiveness of commercial motorcycle averagely complies to road traffic regulations. Also, many of the respondents could not identify and understanding of the road traffic symbols, that is in Ogbomoso there are no road traffic symbols thereby causing accidents.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Education and Training Programs: These programs should focus on promoting road safety, increasing awareness of traffic regulations, and enhancing riding skills to improve the overall safety and professionalism of riders.
2. Access to Formal Education: efforts should be made to provide opportunities for adult education and skill development that is collaborations between local educational institutions, government agencies, and community organizations can facilitate the provision of adult education programs that enable riders to acquire basic literacy and numeracy skills.

1. **Safety Measures and Regulations:** To enhance compliance, there should be targeted campaigns to educate riders about the importance of wearing helmets, registering motorcycles, and obtaining licenses. These campaigns can be conducted through partnerships between government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and local community leaders to ensure a comprehensive and sustainable approach.
2. **Economic Empowerment and Diversification:** Initiatives such as skills training, entrepreneurship development, and access to microfinance can help riders explore alternative income-generating activities, reducing their reliance on commercial motorcycle riding and providing them with greater economic stability.
3. **Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation:** To gauge the effectiveness of interventions and policies, it is crucial to establish a monitoring and evaluation system. Regular assessments should be conducted to measure changes in riders' knowledge, compliance levels, and socio-economic conditions. The data collected can inform adjustments to existing programs and the development of new initiatives, ensuring their relevance and impact over time.

By implementing these recommendations, policymakers, community leaders, and relevant stakeholders can work together to improve the safety, livelihoods, and overall well-being of commercial motorcycle riders in Ogbomosho Metropolis.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] A. D. Bank, "Report on Road Transport in Africa," AFDB, 2022.
- [2] W. H. Organisation, "Evaluation on Road Traffic Injuries," WHO, 2018.
- [3] W. H. Organization, "Reforms on Safety and Mobility," WHO, 2022.
- [4] F. R. S. Act, "www.highwaycode.com.ng," Federal Road Safety Commission, 207. [Online].
- [5] Ebeigbe j A& Obahiagbon E.A, 2012.
- [6] M. Mitka, "Findings on Youth Injuries Bolster Case for Helmet Use by All Motorcycle Riders.," *JAMA*, vol. 2683, p. 304(24), 2010.
- [7] O. K. Sunday, "The performance of the motorcycle rider behavior," *Nigerian Injury Prevention*, Vols. A194-A194, p. 16(Supplement 1), 2010.
- [8] AdesolaA, Imhasoloeva M & Akinsulore A, "Prevalence and correlates of erectile dysfunction among long-distance commercial vehicle drivers and commercial motorcycle riders in Ibadan Nigeria: a comparative cross-sectional study.," *African Health Sciences*, Vols. 1-12, p. 22(3), 2022.

- [9] Achigbu, E Ezepue U, "). Prevalence and severity of pterygium among commercial motorcycle riders in south eastern Nigeria.," *Ghana Medical Journal*, vol. 153, p. 43(3), 2014.
- [10] Prajapati, S., & Nagar, K., "Safety Education on Knowledge, Attitude and Practice," *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, pp. 948-958, 2022.
- [11] Lim, T., Beck, B., Thompson, J., & Tian, L., "A Framework for Describing and Measuring Bike Riders' Stress and Subjective Experiences While Riding.," *Electronic Journal*, no. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4192552>, 2022.
- [12] Yang, Y., Wang, L., Easa, S. M., & Zheng, X., "Analysis of Electric Bicycle," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 5905, p. 19(10), 2022.
- [13] Barone, S & Lo Iacono, "A Framework for Describing and Measuring Bike Riders' Stress and Subjective Experiences While Riding.," *Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing & Service Industries*, vol. 25(2), pp. 239-250, 2023.
- [14] Lemonakis, P., Botzoris, G., Galanis, A., & Eliou, N. , 2021.
- [15] L. T. Ngoan, "'Viet Nam's Mandatory Motorcycle Helmet Law 2007 and its Impact on Road Traffic Injuries Mortality in a Mountainous Province: A Population-Based Mortality Registration, 2005-2018.'" , *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research*, vol. 40(3), no. <https://doi.org/10.26717/bjstr.2021.40.006460>, 2021.
- [16] A. Singh, "Effect of Low Price on Respondents While Purchasing FMCG," *International Journal Of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, vol. 24(5), no. <https://doi.org/10.37200/ijpr/v24i5/pr2020271>, pp. 5658-5663, 2022.
- [17] Almutairi M, Mckenna G & O' Neil, "A comparative examination of the role of need in the relationship between dental service use and socio-economic status across respondents with distinct needs using data from the Scottish Health Survey.," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 23(1), no. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-15078-z>, 2023.
- [18] Koyama, T., Suzuki, T., Yamamori, K., Uematsu, Y., Hirano, S., Ishizaki, N., & Wada, K., "Research on Ultra-High Viscosity Index Engine Oil: Part 2 - Influence of Engine Oil Evaporation Characteristics on Oil Consumption of Internal Combustion Engines.," *SAE International Journal of Advance and Current Practices in Mobility*, vol. 4(4), no. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2022-01-0524>, pp. 1217-1227, 2022.
- [19] J. K. Kumphong, "Correlations Among Motorcycle-Related Deaths, Helmet Law Enforcement and Helmet Usage For Asian Countries.," *International Journal of GEOMATE*, vol. 15(49), no. <https://doi.org/10.21660/2018.49.tr1100>, 2018.
- [20] Yellappan, K., K.C. Mani, K., & Md. Tamrin, S. B. , 2019.
- [21] Burtscher, M., Rued, G., & Nachbauer, W., "). Riding the Narrow Tracks of Moral Life: Commercial Motorbike Riders in Sierra Leone," *Africa Today*, vol. 58(2), no. <https://doi.org/10.2979/africatoday.58.2.59>, 2013.
- [22] Abid M.M, Bano, S, Kumar, A, Iqbal M, Shahid,M.Javed A and Tariq U,R, "Trend towards Helmet Usage and the Behavior of Riders While Wearing Helmets.," *Sustainability*, vol. 14(22), no. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su.142214713>, p. 14713, 2022.
- [23] Pandey, D., Saroshe, S., Dixit, S., & Sabde, Y., "Estimation of prevalence of headphone usage during driving and awareness about their health hazards among medical undergraduates.," *International of Community Medicine and Public Health*, vol. 2(2), p. 167, 2015.
- [24] Kyriakidis, M., Happee, R., & de Winter, J., "Public opinion on automated driving: Results of an international questionnaire among 5000 respondents.," *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, vol. 32, no. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2015.04.014>, pp. 127-140, 2015.

- [25] S. Souche-le corvec, "Why do respondents give non responses to the income question during a transport survey? What can be learned by hurdle models and for respondents' attitudes to pricing change.," *Transportation Letters*, vol. 14(9), no. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19427867.2021.1966720>, pp. 956-971, 2021.
- [26] Karlberg, L., Undén, A. L., Elofsson, S., & Krakau, I., "Is There a Connection Between Car Accidents, Near Accidents, and Type A Drivers?," *Behavioural Medicine*, vol. 24(3), no. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08964289809596387>, pp. 99-106, 1998.
- [27] Rashad, D., Kumar, D., Luff, D., Habib, D., Munaaf, M. H. M., Kumar, D., Chang, D., & "Evaluate the Effect of Bike Riding on Posture.," *International Journal of Contemporary Research and Review*, no. <https://doi.org/10.15520/ijcrr/2018/9/01/398>, 2018.
- [28] Jongen, E. M. M., Brijs, K., Mollu, K., Brijs, T., & Wets, G., "70 km/h Speed Limits on Former 90 km/h Roads.," *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factor and Ergonomics Society*, vol. 53(6), no. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018720811419848>, pp. 71-785, 2011.
- [29] Mumuni, A., Abeebe Adebayo, L., & Mynepalli Kameswara Chandra, S., "Road Use Regulations: Knowledge and Compliance Among Commercial Motorcycle Riders in Oluyole Local Government Area, Ibadan, Nigeria.," *Nigeria Journal of Health and Environmental Research*, no. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.jher.20230901.13>, 2023.
- [30] Hagan, D., Tarkang, E. E., & Aku, F. Y., "Compliance of Commercial Motorcycle Riders with Road Safety Regulations in a Pen-Urban Town in Ghana," *PLOS ONE*, vol. e0246965, no. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246965>, p. 16(3), 2021.
- [31] Ogunkeyede, O. S., & Osungbade, K., "Compliance of Commercial with Motorcyclistwith Road Safety Measures in a Nigerian Metropolitan City," *Traffic Injury Prevention*, vol. 20(Sup2), no. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15389588.2019.1659584>, pp. S174-S176, 2019.
- [32] Elevelt, A., Höhne, J. K., & Blom, A. G., "Squats in Surveys: Investigating the Feasibility of, Compliance With, and Respondents' Performance on Fitness Tasks in Self-Administered Smartphone Surveys Using Acceleration Data.," *Frontier in Public Health*, no. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2021.627509>, 2021.
- [33] M. Sroka, "Transport Safety in Road Traffic - The Condition and Preventive Measures as Assessed by the Respondents.," *System Safety:Human-Technical Facility-Environment*, vol. 4(1), no. <https://doi.org/10.2478/czoto.20220008>, pp. 67-75, 2022.

